

ISSUES OF USE OF THE IPO MECHANISM IN THE INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES

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Abstract. This article explores and analyzes the need for an IPO mechanism to improve the financial performance of joint stock companies. The IPO is being studied, that is, the content of a public offering of shares, its importance and stages of implementation, as well as its advantages and disadvantages in attracting investment to joint stock companies operating in our country. Analyzed the IPO of large companies in world and domestic practice. The article identifies problems in this area and develops the author's proposals and recommendations on them.

Key words: IPO, public offering, Road Show, joint stock companies, companies, prospectus, raising capital, stock market, capital market.

INTRODUCTION

Regardless of the sphere in which the companies operate, the allocation of additional financial resources, including the attraction of foreign investments, remains an important task in our country. One of the most modern ways to attract investments to the same stock companies is to use the IPOMINIM. As the normative-legal basis for the work to be carried out in this regard, we must of course agree with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1] adopted on April 29, 2019

and with the resolution of the PP-4300 on "measures for further improvement of In these normative documents, the following important tasks are defined.

In particular:

- Development of the concept of medium-term and long-term development of the financial market of the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at attracting capital and developing the financial market as an alternative source of free funds of enterprises, financial institutions and the population; IPO), to ensure their access to foreign capital markets;

- creation of an effective competitive environment for sectors of the economy and simplification of the procedure for consideration of documents of business entities in the acquisition of shares and stakes of enterprises that have a leading position in achieving a gradual reduction of monopolies in the market of goods and services;

- sale of state-owned shares (stakes) in the charter capital of chemical and oil and gas industries, business entities in the field of mechanical engineering, banking and insurance organizations;

- Development of ready investment proposals to attract foreign direct investment.

One of the most important of these tasks, of course, is the IPO- (Initial public offering) mechanism, which serves to increase the prestige of joint stock companies. Because today, the continuous attraction of financial resources by joint-stock companies is directly proportional to the development of the Uzbek securities market, in mathematical terms.

REFERENCES

In our study, we examined the views of leading global and local economists on the IPO mechanism, i.e., “Initial public offering” is interpreted as “initial public offering”. In addition, the term "public offering" implies the free trade of shares of joint-stock companies with a large number of institutional and private investors. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Securities Market", adopted on June 3, 2015, defines public placement of securities as an open subscription using advertising among an unlimited number of investors [3]. According to Doctor of Economics, Professor S. Elmiraev, "IPO means the issuer's first public offering of shares in the open market" [4].

Research by foreign economists Allen Michel and Jacob Oded states that an IPO is "one of the most important events in an IPO's activity, and its application is to attract additional financial resources to expand the activities of young and new companies in the future." In another study, leading IP economists Leonella Gori and Emanuele Teti explained that "an IPO is a huge accumulation of money for a strategic investment while the company is operating." A. According to Tsyglin, "an IPO is a public offering of a company's shares on a stock exchange, through which millions of people around the world buy its shares and publicize the company itself." According to O. Lomontatidze, M. Lvova, A. Bolotin, “IPO (Initial Public Offering) is the initial public offering of a company's shares for sale to a wide range of buyers. This means that the company will list its shares on the stock exchange for the first time and offer them to an unlimited number of buyers. ”[8] According to Professor E. Zhukov, Doctor of Economics, "IPO is a type of initial public offering, in the process of which

new shares of the company are always sold" [9]. According to Investopedia, "Initial public offering (IPO) is the process by which a private corporation issues new shares to be offered for sale to the public." [10]

Based on the above, it can be noted that the IPO applies only to the most common type of securities, the stock, and involves the mass sale of shares of a joint stock company on the stock market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this study is to apply the IPO mechanism to increase the efficiency of joint stock companies and optimize the process of attracting investment, as well as to develop scientific and practical proposals and recommendations for the initial public offering of shares in companies. Comparison, grouping, and SWOT analysis methods were widely used in the research process. As a result of the study, scientific and practical proposals were developed on measures to apply the IPO mechanism to increase the efficiency of joint-stock companies and optimize the process of attracting investment.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, the development of the securities market in Uzbekistan is associated with the growing role of financing the activities of joint stock companies. However, one of the most popular and rapidly evolving forms of investment financing is the initial placement of these shares. Although it has long been used in world practice and mass placement is widely used in developed countries, in our country this process is a relatively new financial mechanism, so we believe that it needs to be studied and

researched in more depth. We will first look at what the main purpose of using the IPO mechanism is in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The main objectives of the initial public offering of shares of joint stock companies¹

As can be seen from Figure 1, companies initially publicly place their shares in the stock market through IPOs to attract investment, which in turn not only attracts additional financial resources to joint stock companies, but also contributes to the development of the stock market, including the capital market. Once we have determined the goals of the IPO, we will now examine the initial public placement steps. That is, the initial public offering of shares of companies is carried out in the following stages:

¹Муаллиф томонидан шакллантирилди.

1. Preliminary preparation. Companies must meet certain requirements a few years (usually 1-2 years) prior to the initial public offering of their shares. In particular, joint-stock companies are required to conduct an IPO, such as a clear and well-structured business plan and regular preparation of financial statements.

2. Forming a team to conduct an IPO. At this stage, the company forms a team to help conduct the IPO. The team includes an audit company, an investment bank and a legal aid firm. This team should hold a general meeting 1-2 months before submitting the documents to the Securities Commission. During the meeting, all members of the group will be assigned areas of responsibility, a plan and schedule for the organization of the IPO. Once all members of the team have completed the meeting, the IPO will officially begin.

3. Creating an issue prospectus. This process is a key tool in attracting investors to the company. It should be noted that the issue prospectus requires the most complete and transparent information about the company issuing shares. As a rule, the issue prospectus includes financial reports for the last five years, information about the target audience, key competitors, development prospects and plans, as well as the characteristics of management personnel. At the same time, the investment bank conducts an in-depth analysis of the issuer, carefully examines all available information and then identifies some of the cases to be included in the documents and submits reports to the investor by a legal partner and auditor. Before the final version of the issue prospectus is issued, it must be examined by the relevant Securities Commission. At this stage, the underwriter determines which of the investment

partners will distribute this issue prospectus to potential customers. The issue prospectus will then be sent to investors for consideration.

4. Road Show Conduct Phase. Road Show events and meetings organized in different cities are attended by investors, as well as large depositors such as banks, various funds, insurance corporations. During this period, it is very important to motivate potential customers to buy shares in the company. The Road Show usually lasts about a month. Every day at the Road Show, company management will have to hold at least two meetings with potential stock buyers. This is a very important stage in the preparation of the IPO, and also during this period the underwriter begins to compile the order book. After the Road Show, the company's founders will hold a meeting with representatives of the investment bank, where they will approve the amount of shares issued, as well as what price will be offered to investors. The number of securities and their value are formed on the basis of a preliminary assessment of the demand for them. Once the prices are approved, the final version of the issue prospectus and information on price adjustments are sent to the print media, then approved by the founders and the securities are distributed to customers.

5. Start selling securities. Once the share price is clearly set and approved, the IPO will be announced (as a rule, it will be announced publicly after all trades on the stock exchange are closed). The securities begin to be distributed among the underwriters and their partners. The process of selling shares will begin the next day at the same time as the stock market. At this stage, the leading investment bank must control the sales process, ensuring a stable value of the securities.

6. Make a deal. If the company transfers the block of shares to its underwriter, and the underwriter in turn transfers the funds in full to the company's account, the transaction is considered complete (the process usually takes three days). Exactly one week after the end of the deal, the public offering will be officially announced as successful, and the silence period will end twenty-five days after the IPO begins. Only after this period expires will team members have the right to make a public statement about the company's forecast price, as well as recommend to potential investors to purchase the securities.

At the stages listed above, joint stock companies may initially publicly place their own shareholdings and, as a result, have additional financial resources. Below we review the SWOT analysis of the organization of the IPO mechanism.

Table 1

SWOT analysis of the IPO mechanism ²

Advantages (Strengths)	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attracting large amounts of funds; • increasing the flexibility of the financial structure; • reduction of debt; • achieving high liquidity through share capital; • reputation, recognition and reputation of the company; • there is no risk in raising capital; • The market value of the company is determined. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of optimal distribution of property; • Increasing the company's negotiation capacity; • Achieving long-term development goals; • Achieving high competitiveness in the market; • Encourage managers and employees by creating opportunities to purchase company shares.
Disadvantages (Weaknesses)	Dangerous aspects
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public disclosure of information; • high emission costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • Low valuation of shares; • • Occupied by large companies.

From Table 1 above, we can conclude that the method of applying the IPO mechanism in attracting additional financial resources to joint stock companies, including investments, has its advantages and disadvantages like other methods. However, it should be noted that the advantages of the initial public offering of shares will have a positive impact on its future performance, market position and popularity of the company.

As a result of our research, we analyzed several companies in the world that have focused their shares on trading on major stock exchanges through IPOs. In particular, in Figure 2 below we can see the IPO operations of some of the largest companies in the world.

² Formed by the author.

Figure 2. The largest IPO transactions observed in the world practice, \$ billion³

As can be seen from Figure 2, the largest IPO to date has been held by Saudi Aramco, an oil company from Saudi Arabia. In 2019, Saudi Aramco, the first public offering of its shares on the Saudi Stock Exchange, raised \$ 25.6 billion. By raising capital in the amount of US dollars, it has set a unique record in this regard. The company is valued at \$ 8.53 per share, valued at \$ 1.7 trillion. Priced in U.S. dollars. In addition, the People's Republic of China's Alibaba has invested \$ 25 billion in the top three IPOs. It should be noted that the Industrial and Commercial Bank of the People's Republic of China has attracted capital in the amount of 22.1 billion US dollars.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 2017 "On measures to accelerate the sale of state property and further simplify its procedures" for the first time in the history of the country's stock market and the

³ Formed by the author.

introduction of a secondary (SPO) public offer. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of May 10, 2017 "On the organization of the public offering of shares on the stock exchange", the shares of JSC "Quartz" will be sold by IPO. Initially, JSC "Quartz" produced 4574934 units with a face value of 1715 soums and 7846.01 million soums. The issue of ordinary shares was registered on October 2, 2017 and put up for sale on December 5 at the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent". The selling price of each share is set from 3,000 to 9,100 soums, and the deadline for submission of orders is April 3, 2018. As the method of first public offering (IPO) is implemented for the first time in the history of the stock market of the country, special attention was paid to the quality organization of this process, attracting a wide range of people. According to the results of the IPO, JSC "Quartz" will receive an additional 7,523.81 million soums. soums of working capital. Part of these funds was used to cover the costs of the IPO. The rest was spent on modernization of production facilities at the enterprise, installation of new modern equipment [10]. In addition, the adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No PP-4300 "On measures to further improve the mechanisms for attracting foreign direct investment in the economy of the Republic" has a positive impact on attracting investment in joint stock companies. In particular, according to this decision, state-owned shares (stakes) in the charter capital of business entities offered for sale to investors, including foreign investors, 100% state share in the charter capital of SUE "Shahrisabz Yulduzi", JSC "Kattakurgan Yog-Moy", The state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies such as JSC "Namanganvino", JSC "Kokand Yog-Moy", JSC "Asaka

Yog", JSC "Kokand Mechanical Plant" was put up for sale by the State Assets Management Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan [11].

In our above research, we have witnessed that there are enough problems and controversies today in attracting investments to joint stock companies through the IPO mechanism. In particular, we can give them the following examples:

- First of all, not only non-economists, but also economists do not have a clear idea of what an IPO is;
- Representatives of joint-stock companies operating in the country do not have clear strategies for the purpose of the IPO, its requirements and necessities, that is, they rely only on the old methods of raising capital for their activities;
- Not to use foreign experience in conducting road shows;
- Sust slow implementation of laws and regulations to reduce the state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies through the initial public offering.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, there are a number of pressing issues in attracting investment to the country's joint stock companies, in particular, the main reason for which is the fact that loans from commercial banks still play a key role in attracting capital in JSCs. we can emphasize that.

It is advisable to implement the following proposals related to attracting investment in joint stock companies:

1. It is necessary to ensure that the representatives of different industries are given an understanding of the IPO mechanism through various means;

2. Joint-stock companies operating in our country should develop their own strategy for raising capital and, in turn, give high priority to the application of the IPO mechanism under this strategy;

3. Use of foreign experience in organizing Road Shows during IPOs;

4. It is necessary to strictly control the unconditional implementation of normative and legal acts on reducing the state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4300 of April 29, 2019 "On measures to further improve the mechanisms for attracting foreign direct investment in the economy of the Republic."
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Securities Market" adopted on June 3, 2015, Chapter 3, Article 14.
4. SE Elmiraev "Corporate Finance" textbook: - T .: "Sano-standart" publishing house, 2015. –256 pages.
5. Allen Michel, Jacob Oded, Israel Shaked "Institutional investors and firm performance: Evidence from IPOs". 22 October 2019. Leonella Gori, Emanuele Teti, Andrea Loi, Maurizio Dallochio "Seasonal darkness and IPO" Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization, Volume 178, 2020, Pages 494-508.
6. <https://vc.ru/finance/67476> - chto- takoe-ipo-i-stoit-li-v-nem-prinimat-uchastie-primer-ipo-uber.
7. «Bazoviy kurs po rynku tsennykh bumag: uchebnoe posobie» / O. V. Lomontatidze, M. I. Lvova, A. V. Bolotin et al. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 448s.
8. E.F. Zhukova Rynok tsennykh bumag: uchebnyk dlya studentov vuzov, obuchayushchixsya po ekonomicheskim spetsialnostyam / pod red ..— 3-e izd., Pererab. and dop. - M .: UNITI-DANA, 2009. - 567 p.

<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/ipo.asp>

9. M. Kenjaev "HOW WAS THE FIRST IPO?" Published in the economic newspaper "My property" on May 18, 2018, issue №18.

10. <http://davaktiv.uz/> - Data of the State Assets Management Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan.